

A Dynamic, Nonlinear Model for Optimal Decision-Making

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Abstract--*Decision problems constitute a genre of systems theory which we face everyday in our routine lives. Yet among systems engineers there is disagreement and confusion about how to automate decision processes. This attests to the complexity of many difficult decision problems; finding a common framework for representation will be difficult, if not impossible. In this paper the basic elements of numerical modeling of decision processes shall be briefly discussed. A normative, utility-theoretic perspective shall be followed while issues of nonlinearity, stochastic processes, and dynamic parameters shall be briefly discussed. This paper is intended to illustrate the challenges to putting decision problems on a first principles basis.*

INTRODUCTION

Decision-making in most realms of human endeavor has always been a difficult task. With the advent of many enabling technologies (such as remote sensing, modern communications and digital computers), new challenges have arisen in the area of controlling and allocating distributed resources in dynamic environments. As our ability to model complex processes and to produce flexible, programmable assets grows, we have pushed the complexity of many problems well beyond the ability of human operators to manage. This has introduced the need to automate decision-making and has accordingly opened many perplexing issues for systems engineers.

While decision theory was born in the early era of artificial intelligence and the digital computer, it has not seen a sustained interest in the engineering community. It has been largely perceived as a body of knowledge to aid managers and statistical analysts in non-technical problems. Perhaps this lack of attention results from the breadth of these problems which may cut across several distinct engineering disciplines (i.e., control theory, artificial intelligence, game theory, etc...). Or perhaps this lack of interest results

from the attitude that almost everything is a decision process and to meaningfully deal with such problems one must focus problems on a case-by-case basis. But these arguments are flawed--*computation* is involved in most real-world engineering problems and there have been many benefits reaped from studying computation in a general sense. Similarly, many aspects of decision theory are universal to all decision problems: Information must be gathered and evaluated, a reasoning process must take place allowing us to estimate the state of the environment, and finally an action must be taken in attempts to produce desirable outcomes against some known objectives. Further, solutions to specific problems may lead to general techniques applicable to a wide variety of situations.

Models for DECISION-MAKING

The term "decision-making" is used to refer to activities ranging between extended assessment and deliberation resulting in the selection of a preferred option, to rapid, semi-instinctive, choice of a course of action in a swiftly evolving situation. Modern representations of decision-making range from *normative* models of optimal decision-making to *descriptive* or *prescriptive* models of naturalistic decision-making. Normative approaches are attractive for system analysis because they are formally rigorous and, in theory, amenable to precise analysis. Such approaches, though they may incorporate symbolic constructs, tend to use numerical processing to assess situation and optimize responsive actions. In contrast, *prescriptive* approaches model human decision-making more accurately, often using symbolic reasoning and tending to be rule-based (e.g., expert systems). These systems provide little capability to predict performance in new situations and lack portability. Further, their underlying premise may be flawed: A *human-like* approach may not be the most promising. Studies [1] have shown human biases may restrict the range of options considered, and limit the depth of evaluation.

Humans may prematurely terminate the search by selection of the first satisfactory option and may fail to properly revise beliefs in the face of new evidence. Consequently, the scientific community has become increasingly interested in using normative models to perform intelligent reasoning and management tasks. Before further discussion of normative modelling we may note that several promising approaches, such as fuzzy systems and neural networks, offer hybrids of numerical and symbolically based reasoning.

The Normative Approach

The world has many ways to complicate decision problems, seemingly beyond our ability to solve. For example *decision spaces* (further defined in the next section) may be linear or nonlinear, stationary or nonstationary, multi-leveled with multiple objectives; static or dynamic, interactive or uncorrelated, and large-scaled or infinite dimensional. The juxtaposition of all these considerations may produce a very complex problem. We commonly begin by making assumptions about the problem at hand; we may linearize when confronted with nonlinearities, we may assume processes to be uncorrelated, markovian, and stationary--we can form simpler models and extract information to reach our decision. The alternative is to build highly complex models which capture the nature of the problem more completely, and attempt to find approximate solutions. Rather than address the really difficult problem and find approximate solutions, we generally attempt to solve the simplified system in an exact manner. Thus, even within normative decision-making there is a dichotomy of approaches to complex decision problems. The relative merit of these depends upon the criticality of the system at hand, and is a source of debate in the technical community. This paper explores the latter philosophy involving the construction of an exact (as much as possible) formulation of the problem and a subsequent inexact solution. Investigation of this will lead to a better understanding of our condition in this arena, and perhaps motivate new mathematical techniques which can be brought to bare on this problem.

The association between decision-making and the decision environment may be represented in a general closed-loop form, in which decision-making is based on observations of an environment containing a variety of distinguishable subsystems and environments as shown in figure 1. The decision maker processes known objectives and an environmental state estimate, θ , to produce a decision, x . This process continues iteratively and is complicated by the measurement noise and disturbance inputs.

Figure 1 - Closed-loop Decision-Making

We may enhance this model by considering a resource management decision process. Application of a mathematical, state-space approach which will allow for a more succinct discussion of some of the challenges in intelligent decision-making. This is done in figure 2 below. We define the vector of distributed resource decisions as $x = [x_1 \dots x_n]$ which will specify the states of the n resources. The vector $\theta = [\theta_1 \dots \theta_n]$ represents the true state of the environment. This

Figure 2 - A Resource Manager Example includes an almost infinite number of parameters reflecting current resource performance, weather, and other factors effecting the situation. We denote our estimation of some subset of these parameters as θ' . We will assume that each particular vector x can be assessed by some *cost* or *utility* functions which are the negative of each other. The cost of a distributed decision x_0 will also depend upon the environmental state, θ . In practice there may be multiple objectives such as utilization of resources, reduction of risk, etc. The *true cost function* $F(\theta, x)$ maps the vectors θ and

\mathbf{x} into a *true cost vector* $\mathbf{y} = [y_1 \dots y_m]$ which is used to represent the numerical values for some m objective functions. In practice we cannot always exactly model the true cost of an alternative decision; we shall let $F'(\theta', \mathbf{x})$ represent our *cost function model*, and \mathbf{y}' represent the associated *cost vector*. Ultimately we will wish to prioritize the decision alternatives based upon some scalar cost value rather than the vector \mathbf{y}' . We introduce the *true absolute cost function*, $G(\theta, \phi, \mathbf{y})$, to map the true cost vector \mathbf{y} , to some *true absolute cost*, C (a scalar). This represents a weighting operation which, based upon inputs from the a planner in the form of the objectives vector ϕ , will blend the multiple objectives to form our absolute cost. We may assume that there is some optimal weighting function for each situation we may encounter. Again we can only model the optimal case and we introduce the *absolute cost function model*, $G'(\theta', \phi, \mathbf{y}')$, and the resultant *absolute cost*, C' .

Upon obtaining the absolute cost, C' , we must schedule the optimal decision, \mathbf{x}_{opt} . The control and schedule function must keep a record of the decision - absolute cost pairs $(\mathbf{x} - C')$ over time and choose the one with the lowest cost. Upon implementing that decision we say that \mathbf{x}_{opt} is the *current decision*, denoted as \mathbf{x}_{cur} . This decision is fed back to the sensors and to the options generation part of the resource manager. The option generator takes environmental estimates, θ , and \mathbf{x}_{cur} to produce new options. The option generator may additionally require past decision - cost pairs, either $(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}')$ or $(\mathbf{x} - C')$ to provide a measure of the utility of past options it has generated. We have included one additional element in our resource manager model, the *Information Gatherer*. This function produces situation assessments, combines them with event prediction, opponent diagnosis and any other required environmental estimates/predictions to form what we call the *environmental state estimate*, θ' .

We may note that while this is a general model for resource management, it is greatly simplified since we are assessing costs for static decisions rather than strings of decisions. We are not considering the utility of pre-empting an active resource nor the time-critical environment we are operating in. We have essentially ignored the *temporal element* of the problem. Still, with this simplified model in hand we can make several observations about the challenges of resource management.

1) The determination of the cost modeling functions $F'(\theta', \mathbf{x})$ and $G'(\theta', \phi, \mathbf{y}')$ is critical to the prioritization of options. Recall that we have assumed that there is some true cost function, $F(\theta, \mathbf{x})$

representing the ideal cost mapping. In estimating the cost function we are introducing an error, $\epsilon_i = F(\theta, \mathbf{x}) - F'(\theta', \mathbf{x})$. We then compound this error by using the resultant cost estimate in the absolute cost function: $C' = G'(\theta', \phi, \mathbf{y}' + \epsilon_i)$. The total error is then $\epsilon = C - C'$. It would be beneficial to have some strategies for estimating the cost model function and absolute cost function and to develop some error bounds.

2) The cost model functions $F'(\bullet)$ and $G'(\bullet)$ are really some functional mapping from the *decision space* to the *cost space* ($\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{y}'$) and from the *cost space* to the *absolute cost space* ($\mathbf{y}' \rightarrow C'$). One serious problem is that these functional mappings may, in general, be nonlinear. This nonlinearity results from many factors including the higher utility in a synergistic use of resources and the interactive nature of the problem. Most resource managers attempt to decompose the decision problem into constituent pieces, find some optimal decision for each portion, and then to superimpose the resulting decisions, often getting decidedly sub-optimal results. We cannot make a partial decision, $\mathbf{x}_1 \subset \mathbf{x}_0$, and a second partial decision $\mathbf{x}_2 \subset \mathbf{x}_0$ and expect that $Cost(\mathbf{x}_1) + Cost(\mathbf{x}_2) = Cost(\mathbf{x}_0)$. This is because in general

$$G'(\theta', \phi', F'(\theta', \mathbf{x}_0)) \neq G'(\theta', \phi', F'(\theta', \mathbf{x}_1)) + G'(\theta', \phi', F'(\theta', \mathbf{x}_2))$$

3) A related problem is in the options generation portion of the model. Realizing that we are sometimes operating under a severe time constraint we generally cannot examine all the possible decisions (which may themselves be infinite). A graph of a complex, nonlinear absolute cost function over a two-dimensional decision space is shown in figure 3 to illustrate the problem.

Figure 3 - Complex, Nonlinear Decision Space

We would ideally like to schedule the particular decision corresponding to the global minimum. However this may not be possible since for nonlinear functions finding the global minimum may be difficult. It would be beneficial to construct efficient search strategies which could identify local minima over the largest possible range. These search strategies would need to adapt to the changing time constraints for different environmental states. This search may need to be done in the absence of any clear options generation model and thus hints at a heuristic approach.

4) As mentioned earlier, our model does not address the temporal element of the problem. We may obtain optimal decisions at each time step but after their execution we may have implemented a sub-optimal string of decisions. It would be advantageous to look at the cost for a sequence of decisions but since we are constrained by time we can only look at a limited sequence size. The controller/scheduler can only consider a limited number of decision-cost pairs, again due to the time constraints. The inclusion of this temporal element into some general model, and the necessity to adapt to changing time-constraints is a significant problem in resource management.

5) The high level parameter estimation in figure 2 above constitutes a significant challenge. The estimation of the environmental parameter, θ , is exacerbated by the interactive nature of the problem and the dependence upon the *behavior* of adversaries. Our ability to estimate and predict human behavior is, of course, quite limited. We would be interested in robust parameter estimation methodologies able to deal with the various types of error introduced in this estimation process: estimation error, modeling error, and event prediction error.

Utility Theory

Normative decision approaches hypothesize a super decision maker capable of producing optimal decisions. This is appropriate for problems in which a single preference structure is commonly held to be correct or where deviations in preference are inconsequential and kept to a minimum. A *Utility Function* is used to assess the desirability of options. We cite the basic tenets of utility theory here [3], more thorough discussions may be found in [2] and elsewhere.

We assume that the environment can be in any number of states, Θ . The set of actions available to the decision maker may be denoted \mathbf{X} . In the simplest case, taking an action $x \in \mathbf{X}$ when nature is in some

state $\theta \in \Theta$ results in a unique outcome, o , from the a set of outcomes, \mathbf{O} , according to a simple rule of the form

$$o = f(x, \theta)$$

More generally, we may suppose that the result of action is unpredictable, and that an action results in a distribution, L , from some set, Γ , of distributions over o .

A *rational* decision maker is defined as one which can establish preferences, represented here by $<$, among the possible outcomes, i.e., over Γ . In order to solve a decision problem, this preference ordering must admit a real-valued utility function $U: o \rightarrow \Re$ such that, if $L_1 < L_2$, then

$$E^{L_1}(U(o)) < E^{L_2}(U(o))$$

There are a number of collections of conditions under which this is true. These are listed in [3]. We define the decision-theoretic utility function as a function $u: P \times A \rightarrow \Re$ such that, if $F(x, q) = o$, $o \sim L$ (o is a random variable with distribution L), then

$$u(x, \theta) = E^L(U(o))$$

Typically utilities are specified in their functional form without any recourse to U .

Throughout the remainder of this paper we will study graphs and briefly examine mathematical issues such as linearity, preference, games and chaos.

MODELING CONCEPTS/ISSUES

Assume an objective function over a finite parameter space is shown in figures 4-7 below. Suppose that we have control over the (vector) parameter X , and that the parameters, Θ , are the product of the environment and not directly under our control. Our goal is to maximize the utility of a decision by picking the best possible value for X .

If the utility function were linear over the decision space, the optimal decision would be quite easy to find--with some simple estimation we could learn the surface shown in figure 4 below.

Figure 4 - Linear Utility Function

The decision may be complicated by introducing stochastic components to the utility function--these need not be stationary. This is shown in figure 5 below.

Figure 5 - Linear Utility with Random Component

The situation can become appreciably more complicated when nonlinearities enter into the utility function. Figures 6 and 7 show two such nonlinear utility functions.

Figure 6 - Nonlinear Utility Function #1

Figure 7 - Nonlinear Utility Function #2
We may examine the effects of preference by utilizing

three different decision rules for each of these nonlinear utilities. Recall that we may vary only the parameter X in affecting a decision. The preferences are listed below: 1) choose X to maximize the expected value of the utility; 2) choose X in order to maximize the minimum value of the utility; and 3) find any value of X which allows for some minimum number of outcomes to be above a specified threshold. Figure 8 below shows the derived utility for the nine possible choices for X (integers in {0,9}).

Figure 8 - Comparison of Decision Rules

We may observe that for the first nonlinear utility space, setting X=7 is the preferred decision using the expected value and minmax preferences. The threshold preference produces a range of values which would be considered equally desirable. For the second nonlinear utility we find some interesting results. Using the expected value criterion we find that X=7 is the preferred option while X=8 is preferred by the minmax criterion. The threshold preference accepts the choices X=3 and X=8 equally, with no preference. Interestingly, the expected value and minmax criteria result in different choices (X=7, X=8 respectively) while the threshold criterion accepts the minmax choice of X=8 and X=3 equally well. It is important to note that the preference employed may be critical to determining the final decision.

REFERENCES

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